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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

THE PURGATORY OF ST. PATRICK, A COMMON SOURCE FOR BOTH GUERRINO THE WRETCH AND ANTOINE DE LA SALE?¹

1. The legend of the Apennine Sibyl and the Purgatory of St. Patrick

In studying the legend of the Apennine Sibyl, we saw that Guerrino the Wretch and the knights described by Antoine de La Sale have something in common with earlier knights: Huon of Bordeaux and Huon d'Auvergne, the main characters of French-Italian epic poems included in older manuscripts. Explorations into fairy kingdoms inhabited by evil queens or maidens whose name is "Sebile", magical metal rotating devices, enchanted bridges as narrow as razors, visits to the Pope: all sounds really familiar to the ears of a scholar practising the grounds of the Italian Apennine Sibyl legend.

And now we come to Owein.

Owein: another knight, another brave adventurer, another chivalric character described in ancient manuscripts, performing his deeds within one of the earliest traditions of European Middle Ages. A knight not belonging to the French-Italian tradition we have already considered: instead, he is coming straight from the old lore of gaelic Ireland.

Actually this knight is a very special one: he travelled into the netherworld, and his travel appears to be connected to the journeys of Guerrino the

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Wretch and the explorations of Antoine de La Sale's knights into the bowels of Mount Sibyl.

Owein has something to do with the Apennine Sibyl.

We are going to achieve an astounding travel into northern-European realms that are not so easily encountered in the sibilline lore: nonetheless, we will show that the fifteenth-century tales of the Apennine Sibyl are strongly influenced, and in some cases determined, by this absolutely older literary tradition, stemming from ancient Irish legends. An incredible link between the North and the South of Europe, in a common framework of legendary lore: ancient Eire calls the Italian Apennines, and we find evidence that that call was answered.

Our travel begins in a specific place, a remote spot lost in an isolated corner of Europe: Lough Derg, a lake in County Donegal, Ireland. In this lake, there was (and it is still believed to be) a very special place: a subterranean site, a cavern, which provided an access to a world that does not belong to the world of living men.

It was the entrance to the Purgatory: the Purgatory of St. Patrick.

This legend belongs to the most ancient traditions of Ireland, possibly dating back to the fifth century A.D., when St. Patrick came to Ireland to convert the heathens to the new Christian faith. A tradition which, for more than a thousand years, attracted to this far-away site an uninterrupted flow of pilgrims, knights, aristocrats wishing to gain an absolution for their sinful lives. And to experience the adventures of Owein: the knight who entered the netherworld, the Purgatory, and lived to tell.

A distant, secluded, inhabited point of Europe. Just like the Monti Sibillini, in the Italian Apennines.

A gloomy cavern, the entrance to a world of supernatural evil, inhabited by demons. Just like the dark, wicked court of the Apennine Sibyl.

A magical, subterranean realm. Just like the underground kingdom of the Sibyl of the Apennines.

A daring knight, who creeps into subterranean recesses. Just like Guerrino the Wretch and the German knight described by Antoine de La Sale.

A compelling, best-selling tale about the Purgatory of St. Patrick narrated in dozens of literary witnesses throughout the centuries. Just like the story of the Apennine Sibyl.

So, the Purgatory of St. Patrick seems to show close resemblances to our Apennine Sibyl.

And, by all appearances, if you look at the miniatures showing Owein as he enters the Irish Purgatory and Antoine de La Sale creeping into the Sibyl's cave (see figure), the correspondence seems to be striking.

Fig. 1 - The opening of the "Noble et merueilleuse histoire du Purgatoire Saint Patrice" contained in Manuscript no. Fr 1544 (Folium 105 recto) dating to the fourteenth century preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France, and a similar miniature contained in the Chantilly manuscript of Antoine de La Sale's "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl"

But the earliest traces of the Sibyl are contained in fifteenth-century works such as "Guerrino the Wretch" and "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl". On the contrary, the tale of Owein and his exploration of the Purgatory of St. Patrick is contained in much older manuscripts, dating to the second half of the twelfth century. A much older story.

Did the more ancient Purgatory of St. Patrick inspire the subsequent narratives on the Apennine Sibyl's legend?

The answer is yes, as we will demonstrate in subsequent articles.

2. A link between Ireland and Italy

«Moreover there is a rocky cavern, as small as a small house, with an arched roof so low that a tall man would not be able to stand in an upright position [...] under which some say is found an abyss or pit [...] that was opened up by God for the dread of the heathens [...] A certain knight named Owain [...] said [...] “so as to deserve the pardon for my sins, the Purgatory of St. Patrick I want to enter”» («Est autem caverna ipsa lapidea, domuncula tam angustis lateribus, et fornice tam depressa, ut homo procerae staturae adeo se erigere non posset [...] sub quo produnt aliqui subesse voraginem illam et foveam [...] ad terrorem obstinatorum aperuit Deus [...] Miles quidam Oenus nomine [...] respondit [...] ut peccatorum meorum merear remissionem accipere, Purgatorium sancti Patricii volo intrare»).

This is an excerpt from the “Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii” (“Essay on the Purgatory of St. Patrick”), an Irish legend reported in antique manuscripts and dating back at least to the twelfth century: a story of caves, hidden subterranean realms inhabited by demons, and daring knights who venture into frightful hollows.

Has the “Purgatory of St. Patrick” anything to do with the legend of the Apennine Sibyl?

The answer is yes. Let's find out why.

According to an ancient Irish tradition, the “Purgatory of St. Patrick” is an entry point to the supernatural world. When St. Patrick, who lived in the early fifth century A.D., came to Ireland to announce the new Christian faith to the pagan natives, he was jeered by the populace and told they would never believe in his God unless he proved he was able to enter the other world and come back to tell.

God himself appeared to Patrick in a dream to provide him with a suitable reply to the heathens and their challenge: He led him to a place where the entrance to the Purgatory was hidden inside a cave. God told St. Patrick that anyone who entered the cave and stayed in the Purgatory a day and a night would be granted the pardon for all his sins. The gloomy pit contained frightful visions of demons and fiends delivering unbearable tortures to the souls of the damned, and as the scornful Irishmen saw the Purgatory, they believed in the new faith brought to them by St. Patrick, and all became Christian.

Thus, the Purgatory of St. Patrick was a passage from our real world into a magical, supernatural realm, just like the Sibyl's cave. And - just like the cavern on Mount Sibyl, Italy - the Purgatory was to be found in an existing, physical place: a small island, in the middle of a lake - an existing lake, Lough Derg, Co. Donegal, Ireland (see image).

Many centuries ago, Lough Derg was a most remote place to reach for pilgrims headed to the legendary Purgatory: «I thought indeed to go and return [from Dublin] in three weeks at the longest», wrote an ancient Italian visitor, Antonio Giovanni di Mannini, in 1411, «but through the perilous roads and other occasions we have spent three months and a half in going and returning». Today, things are obviously easier: an uninterrupted flow of thousands and thousands of pilgrims still comes every year to this place and the church built on the old cave's site to have their sins forgiven.

Why was this secluded spot of Ireland so renowned - and still is?

Actually its fame as a magical place had a peculiar boost in the twelfth century (apparently two centuries earlier than the Apennine Sibyl in Italy), when the “*Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*” by Henry of Saltrey began to circulate in various manuscripted Latin versions. This work, describing the deeds of a knight called Owain during his visit in the Purgatory, was a best-seller for many centuries, with hundreds of Latin manuscripts reporting this same story and many translations in other European languages.

The tale of Owain, who had explored the Purgatory and seen the punishment of sinners with his earthly eyes, was known throughout

Europe. And people flocked to Lough Derg from remote countries to obtain the remission of their sins: a flow which reminds us what will happen, centuries later, in the area of the Sibyl's cave (though with extremely smaller numbers of visitors).

Fig. 2 - Lough Derg in Ireland and Mount Sibyl in Italy: two sites, both representing an entryway to subterranean, magical realms

The remarkable fact is that we find some peculiar similarities between selected aspects appearing in Owain's tale and specific episodes reported in Antoine de La Sale's "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl" and Andrea da Barberino's "Guerrino The Wretch": a sign that the two authors who wrote about the Apennine Sibyl knew well the legend narrated in "The Purgatory".

And used a few ideas drawn from the ancient Irish tale into the Italian one. A topic that will be thoroughly explored in subsequent articles.

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